

Enhancing Private Key Cryptosystems: A Secure Approach with Pairwise Coprime Moduli

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Abstract

In our previous work, “Enhancing Communication Security: A Private Key Cryptosystem Employing the CRT,” we developed a private key encryption scheme using distinct prime moduli. While primes offer structured mathematical properties, their identification for large numbers is computationally demanding. In this work, we extend our approach by replacing prime moduli with pairwise co-prime integers, eliminating the need for primality testing and simplifying key selection. This extension not only avoids the complexity of choosing large primes but also enhances security by allowing greater flexibility in modulus selection, as any set of pairwise coprime integers can be used. Unlike factorization-dependent cryptosystems, our scheme ensures that neither the individual moduli nor their product is exposed, rendering standard factorization-based attacks ineffective. We analyze the theoretical foundation, security implications, and computational efficiency of this modified scheme, demonstrating its advantages for secure communication.

Keywords: Private Key Cryptosystem, Modular Arithmetic, Chinese Remainder Theorem, Pairwise Co-prime Moduli, and Secure Communication.

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1 Introduction

Cryptography has been used for centuries to secure communication, initially serving military and government purposes. Ancient rulers and states employed cryptographic techniques to protect sensitive information during diplomatic and wartime communications [1]. Over time, cryptography evolved beyond military applications, becoming a fundamental tool for securing digital communication. In the modern digital era, cryptography is ubiquitous, used in messaging applications, financial transactions, cloud storage, and privacy protection mechanisms [2, 3].

Cryptosystems are broadly classified into symmetric key cryptography and asymmetric key cryptography. In symmetric key cryptography, both enciphering and deciphering are done using the same secret key. While this method ensures efficient encryption, it needs a safe mechanism for interchanging the key, which is challenging in large-scale communication networks [12]. To address this, public key cryptography was introduced, where enciphering and deciphering incorporate different keys. The Diffie-Hellman key exchange which was put forth in 1976, laid the foundation for public key cryptosystems, allowing secure key exchange between two parties over an insecure channel [5]. The first practical asymmetric key cryptosystem, RSA, was introduced in 1978 and became widely adopted for secure communication [6]. Several public key cryptographic schemes have since been developed, including Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), which provide equivalent security to RSA with smaller key sizes, and NTRU, a lattice-based cryptosystem designed for post-quantum security [7, 8]. However, public key cryptography is computationally expensive, making it significantly less suitable for encrypting large data directly. Instead, it is often used for key exchange, while private key cryptography is employed for efficient data encryption.

For practical encryption needs, private key cryptosystems such as DES, AES, Blowfish, and ChaCha20 are commonly used. Due to the small key space of DES, AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) was introduced as a more secure alternative [9, 10, 11]. Blowfish gained popularity due to its fast key setup and flexible key size, while ChaCha20 became known for its efficiency on low-power devices and high-speed encryption [12, 13]. However, most private key cryptosystems do not employ deep algebraic structures, number theory, or advanced

mathematical concepts as extensively as public key cryptosystems.

In our earlier work [14], we proposed a private-key cryptosystem based on modular arithmetic properties. The encryption process in that system relied on modular arithmetic, utilizing k distinct prime numbers along with an additional integer that is co-prime to and greater than all the chosen primes. The decryption mechanism was on the basis of the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT). The security of the key was enhanced by keeping the modulus values of all primes and the additional integer secret. Furthermore, each plaintext unit is encrypted into a ciphertext tuple of size k . Upon receiving the ciphertext, it must be divided into blocks of size k , with k itself remaining undisclosed, thereby enhancing security.

In this paper, we extend our previous approach by replacing prime numbers with arbitrary co-prime integers. One of the main limitations of our prior scheme was the requirement to select prime numbers. To ensure security, large primes had to be chosen, and since these primes were essential components of the key, frequent key changes necessitated repeated primality testing, increasing computational complexity. Key generation, therefore, became a challenging task. To mitigate this issue, our proposed approach selects k co-prime integers instead of primes. Using of co-primes allows great flexibility in selecting the key also meanwhile allowing Decryption from the set of large random integers. Therefore the modification alongside simplifying the process of key generation the co-primality brings in an additional layer of randomness leading to enhanced security.

We will provide a systematic analysis of proposed approach in this paper of writing, by emphasizing its structural advantages, computational feasibility and security implications while at the same time expatiating on the proposals' possible weaknesses and future work.

2 Preliminaries

Having introduced the new cryptosystem, this section embodies background math. Not only does it serve as an introduction, but also an integral part for understanding what is to follow in subsequent chapters. These include co-prime integers, the Chinese remainder theorem (CRN for short) and examples of its solution; calculation modulus etc... these make up background mathematics necessary for any modern-day number theory specialist. [15, 16].

2.1 Coprime Integers

Lets say a and b are two positive integers and if 1 is their greatest common divisor (GCD) they are said to be coprime (or relatively prime), which can be expressed as -

$$\gcd(a, b) = 1.$$

In cryptographic and modular arithmetic application these kind of numbers play a crucial role. Notably in number theory.

2.2 Euclid's Lemma

If $a \mid bc$ and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, then $a \mid c$ for all $a, b, c \in \mathbb{Z}$.

The transposition of Euclid's Lemma is: For any $a, b, c \in \mathbb{Z}$, if $a \nmid c$ and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, then $a \nmid bc$.

2.3 Modular Arithmetic

Modular arithmetic, in mathematics is a system where numbers are computed within the boundary of a fixed number, defined by a modulus. Lets say, for integer n , modular arithmetic in general operates on integers which produce identical remainders upon dividing by the modulus n . We say that these integers belong to the same equivalence classes.

Though residues of n an altogether a new perspective can be give to clock arithmetic , which consists of

$$\{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}.$$

If any two integers say a and b generate the identical remainders upon dividing by n , then they considered to be congruent modulo n , whcih can be wirtten as,

$$a \equiv b \pmod{n} \quad \text{if and only if} \quad n \text{ divides } (a - b).$$

In modular arithmetic the basic operations like addition, subtraction and multiplication hold good:

$$(a \pm b) \pmod n = [(a \pmod n) \pm (b \pmod n)] \pmod n,$$

$$(a \cdot b) \pmod n = [(a \pmod n) \cdot (b \pmod n)] \pmod n.$$

Due to its periodic nature, modular arithmetic is largely incorporated in cryptography and computational number theory. Since the modular arithmetic has the periodic nature it is extensively used in applications of computational number theory and cryptographic applications.

2.4 Congruences and Modular Inverses

Lets consider a set of modular congruences as follows,

$$ax \equiv b \pmod n$$

and we can say that it is solvable provided that the greatest common divisor of a and n divides b . If a and n are adhere co-primality, the a unique modular inverse is present for a modulo n . This modular inverse, represented as a^{-1} , indemnifies the following relation,

$$aa^{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod n.$$

In particular, modular inverses are handy in solving the congruences and key generation in cryptographic applications.

2.5 Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT)

To fix a set of modular congruences given simultaneously, there is a technique to solve it and the Chinese Remainder Theorem offers a path to achieve this.

$$x \equiv a_1 \pmod{n_1}, \quad x \equiv a_2 \pmod{n_2}, \quad \dots, \quad x \equiv a_k \pmod{n_k}$$

where n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k adhere co-primality pairwise, CRT assures that a distinct solution exists for modulo N , where N is the product of the moduli:

$$N = n_1 n_2 \dots n_k.$$

2.6 Solution to the Chinese Remainder Theorem

The following formula provides a solution for the set of congruence under the Chinese Remainder Theorem,

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^k a_i N_i y_i \pmod N,$$

Here $N_i = \frac{N}{n_i}$ and y_i is the modular inverse of N_i modulo n_i , which satisfies

$$N_i y_i \equiv 1 \pmod{n_i}.$$

Using the moduli from the set of congruences, this approach dexterously rebuilds x , making it feasible in various cryptographic applications.

3 Extended Private Key Cryptosystem Using Pairwise Co-Prime Moduli

We introduce a private key Cryptosystem, which utilizes pairwise co-prime integers to replace the prime moduli, in an extension of the earlier work. The new scheme proposed in this paper is based on algorithms of modular arithmetic and produces a symmetric encryption algorithm that allows more freedom in the encryption key, k pairwise co-prime integers n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k , each n_i is greater than 128, along with an integer a such that $a > n_i$ and $\gcd(a, n_i) = 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$ is included in the key.

Based upon the ASCII encoding scheme, the characters of the plain text are charted to its corresponding ASCII value. Later these characters of the cipher texts are arranged into the blocks of the size k , and these blocks represent the unit of the encrypted plain-text. Here k remains secret adding to the security of the system. The following section discusses in detail the mode of generating the keys, encryption, decryption, the computational complexity and the analysis of the security. Additionally, the implementation of an example is given. To validate the correctness of enciphering and deciphering operations, a python based algorithm is also given.

3.1 Algorithm

3.1.1 Key Generation

- Select k random integers n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k , to ensure these are pairwise co-prime and each one of them satisfies $n_i > 128$.
- Choose an integer a such that $\gcd(a, n_i) = 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $a > n_i$ for all i .

Thus, the key is represented as $(a, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$.

3.1.2 Pseudocode for Key Generation

Algorithm 1 Key Generation

```

1: procedure KEYGENERATION( $k$ )
2:   Input: Number of moduli  $k$ 
3:   Output: Key  $(a, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ 
4:   Initialize an empty list moduli
5:   for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
6:     Select a random integer  $n_i > 128$ 
7:     while  $n_i$  is not coprime with all existing moduli do
8:       Select a new random  $n_i > 128$ 
9:     end while
10:    Add  $n_i$  to moduli
11:  end for
12:  Select a random integer  $a$  such that  $a > \max(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ 
13:  while  $\gcd(a, n_i) \neq 1$  for any  $i$  from 1 to  $k$  do
14:    Select a new random  $a > \max(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ 
15:  end while
16:  return  $(a, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ 
17: end procedure

```

3.1.3 Encryption

Let P be a plaintext unit, and let p denote its numerical equivalent based on the ASCII mapping. The encryption process transforms p into the ciphertext as follows:

$$a \cdot p \equiv c_1 \pmod{n_1}, \quad a \cdot p \equiv c_2 \pmod{n_2}, \quad \dots, \quad a \cdot p \equiv c_k \pmod{n_k}.$$

Thus, each plaintext unit P is encrypted into the tuple (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k) , which forms the corresponding ciphertext.

3.1.4 Pseudocode for Encryption

Algorithm 2 Encryption

```

1: procedure ENCRYPT(plaintext,  $a, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k$ )
2:   Input: Plaintext string, key  $(a, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ 
3:   Output: Ciphertext list
4:   Initialize an empty list ciphertext
5:   for each character  $P$  in plaintext do
6:     Compute  $p = \text{ASCII value of } P$ 
7:     Initialize tuple  $c = []$ 
8:     for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
9:       Compute  $c_i = (a \cdot p) \bmod n_i$ 
10:      Append  $c_i$  to  $c$ 
11:    end for
12:    Append  $c$  to ciphertext
13:  end for
14:  return ciphertext
15: end procedure

```

3.1.5 Decryption

Since $\gcd(a, n_i) = 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$, the modular inverse of a modulo each n_i exists. Let these modular inverses be a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k , satisfying:

$$a \cdot a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{n_i}, \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq i \leq k.$$

To recover the original plaintext value p , fix the system of modular congruences using the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT):

$$x \equiv a_1 c_1 \pmod{n_1}, \quad x \equiv a_2 c_2 \pmod{n_2}, \quad \dots, \quad x \equiv a_k c_k \pmod{n_k}.$$

Since the moduli are pairwise coprime, CRT guarantees a distinct solution x modulo $N = n_1 n_2 \dots n_k$, which yields p . The corresponding ASCII character of p reconstructs the original plaintext unit P .

This process is applied to each plaintext unit iteratively to obtain the complete ciphertext during encryption and to retrieve the original message during decryption.

3.1.6 Pseudocode for Decryption

Algorithm 3 Decryption

```

1: procedure DECRYPT(ciphertext,  $a, n_1, \dots, n_k$ )
2:   Input: Ciphertext list, key  $(a, n_1, \dots, n_k)$ 
3:   Output: Plaintext string
4:   plaintext  $\leftarrow$  empty string;  $N \leftarrow \prod_{i=1}^k n_i$ 
5:   for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
6:      $a_i \leftarrow$  modular inverse of  $a \pmod{n_i}$ 
7:   end for
8:   for each block  $(c_1, \dots, c_k)$  in ciphertext do
9:     congruences  $\leftarrow [(a_i \cdot c_i \pmod{n_i}, n_i)$  for  $i = 1$  to  $k]$ 
10:     $x \leftarrow$  ChineseRemainderTheorem(congruences)
11:    if  $0 \leq x \leq 127$  then
12:      plaintext  $\leftarrow$  plaintext + chr( $x$ )
13:    else
14:      error "invalid ciphertext"
15:    end if
16:  end for
17:  return plaintext
18: end procedure
19: procedure CHINESEREMAINDERTHEOREM(congruences)
20:   Input: List of  $(a_i, n_i)$  pairs
21:   Output:  $x \pmod{N}$ 
22:    $N \leftarrow \prod n_i$ ;  $x \leftarrow 0$ 
23:   for each  $(a_i, n_i)$  in congruences do
24:      $N_i \leftarrow N/n_i$ ;  $y_i \leftarrow$  modular inverse of  $N_i \pmod{n_i}$ 
25:      $x \leftarrow x + a_i \cdot N_i \cdot y_i$ 
26:   end for
27:   return  $x \pmod{N}$ 
28: end procedure

```

Due to the uniqueness of the solution guaranteed by the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT), decryption always retrieves the original plaintext unit accurately. Since the highest numerical value of ASCII characters is 127, and during encryption, each plaintext unit (represented as its ASCII numerical equivalent) is multiplied by a , ensuring a maximum product of $127a$, the moduli n_i must be chosen appropriately. To prevent any partial information about the key from being exposed, each n_i is selected such that $n_i > 128$ and $a > n_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$.

For instance, under the condition that each $n_i > 128$, it follows that n_i does not divide any integer between 1 and 127. Additionally, since $\gcd(a, n_i) = 1$ for all i , Euclid's Lemma ensures that n_i does not divide $p \cdot a$ for any plaintext unit p within this range. Consequently, no ciphertext tuple contains a zero value. Furthermore, as the ASCII character 0 is not used for communication, the presence of a zero in the ciphertext would indicate that one of the moduli divides a number between 1 and 127, potentially revealing partial key information. Moreover,

if a is not greater than n_i for all i , then for cases where $p = 1$ and $a < n_i$, the computation $(p \cdot a) \bmod n_i$ results in a , thereby exposing partial information about the key. Ensuring $a > n_i$ for all i takes out this susceptibility and improves the security of the cryptosystem.

3.2 Complexity Analysis

Here we discuss the analysis of the computational complexity of the proposed cryptosystem with respect to enciphering and deciphering. The number of modular operations determine the complexity during the decryption and the encryption processes.[17].

3.2.1 Encryption

Assume that the plaintext consist of k' characters. Every unit of the plain text is encrypted by multiplying its numerical ASCII value by a and computing the result modulo n_i for all i . This arises in a ciphertext tuple of size k for each unit of the plain-text. Since this process is recurs for all k' characters, the sum number of modular multiplications executed is:

$$\mathcal{O}(k'k)$$

Each modular multiplication $p \cdot a \bmod n_i$ involves both multiplication of integers and modular reduction. The multiplication step takes at most $\mathcal{O}(\log a \log p)$ time, and since p is an ASCII value (bounded by 127), it is considered a constant. The modular reduction step requires $\mathcal{O}((\log a)^2)$ using standard division-based methods.

Thus, the overall encryption complexity is:

$$\mathcal{O}(k'k(\log a)^2)$$

since $a > \max(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$.

3.2.2 Decryption

Decryption involves processing the ciphertext, which consists of $k' \cdot k$ values in total. These values are divided into k' blocks, each containing k values. The decryption process applies the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT) to each block to recover the corresponding plaintext unit.

Since solving a system of k modular congruences using CRT requires computing modular inverses and performing modular multiplications, the computational complexity per plaintext unit is approximately:

$$\mathcal{O}((\log N)^2)$$

where $N = n_1 n_2 \cdots n_k$ is the product of all moduli. Repeating this process for k' plaintext units, the final decryption complexity is:

$$\mathcal{O}(k'(\log N)^2)$$

Thus, decryption requires slightly more computation than encryption due to the CRT step but remains efficient for practical applications.

3.3 Security and Limitations

The soundness of the proposed Cryptosystem is boosted by keeping the moduli values secret and selecting them in a non-ordered, random manner, subject only to the condition that they are pairwise relatively prime. Additionally, the scheme introduces a randomly chosen integer a , which is relatively prime and greater than all selected integers. The secrecy of both a and the moduli further strengthens the key space.

During the deciphering, upon obtaining the complete encrypted text corresponding to the plaintext, the one who receives must first partition the ciphertext into blocks of size k . Since the value of k is not disclosed, this further contributes to the secrecy of the scheme. The combination of these factors results in an expanded key space, thereby improving security. Compared to our previous work, where primes were selected in increasing order, the current approach introduces greater randomness by allowing arbitrary selection of pairwise coprime integers. This provides flexibility in key selection while maintaining security.

However, an inherent drawback of this scheme is the increased ciphertext size. Since each plaintext unit produces k ciphertext values, the storage requirements grow with larger values of k and larger integers. This may introduce additional challenges in terms of storage efficiency in practical implementations.

3.4 Example

For the purpose of understanding, we are using small integers for the example. Larger integers can be used in the Python implementation discussed in the next section. In this example, we take three moduli, i.e., $k = 3$, with the following values for the moduli and the multiplier a :

$$n_1 = 1177, \quad n_2 = 3131, \quad n_3 = 327, \quad a = 16441$$

Thus, the key is (1177, 3131, 327, 16441).

We now proceed to encipher and decipher the message "Mathematics" using this key. The plain text units are represented by their ASCII values, and the corresponding encrypted values for each modulus are computed. The following table illustrates the encryption process:

Plaintext(P)	ASCII Mapping(p)	$a \cdot p \pmod{n_1}$	$a \cdot p \pmod{n_2}$	$a \cdot p \pmod{n_3}$
M	77	682	1033	140
a	97	1119	1098	325
t	116	416	377	92
h	104	860	338	308
e	101	971	1111	35
m	109	675	1137	109
a	97	1119	1098	325
t	116	416	377	92
i	105	823	1124	72
c	99	1045	2670	180
s	115	453	2722	1

Therefore, the numerical ciphertext is: [682, 1033, 140, 1119, 1098, 325, 416, 377, 92, 860, 338, 308, 971, 1111, 35, 675, 1137, 109, 1119, 1098, 325, 416, 377, 92, 823, 1124, 72, 1045, 2670, 180, 453, 2722, 1].

For the decryption, we need to find the multiplicative inverses a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 of a modulo n_1 , n_2 , and n_3 respectively. We have:

$$a_1 = 668, \quad a_2 = 482, \quad a_3 = 115$$

Since $k = 3$, we divide the numerical ciphertext of the given plaintext message into blocks of size three. Suppose each block is represented as (c_1, c_2, c_3) . For each block, we need to solve the set of congruences:

$$x \equiv a_1 c_1 \pmod{n_1}, \quad x \equiv a_2 c_2 \pmod{n_2}, \quad x \equiv a_3 c_3 \pmod{n_3}$$

The solution is given by the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT) as:

$$x = a_1 c_1 N_1 y_1 + a_2 c_2 N_2 y_2 + a_3 c_3 N_3 y_3 \pmod{N}$$

where:

$$N_1 = 1023837, \quad N_2 = 384879, \quad N_3 = 3685187, \quad N = 1205056149$$

and the coefficients y_1 , y_2 , and y_3 are given as:

$$y_1 = 100, \quad y_2 = 950, \quad y_3 = 200$$

Now, let's create a table that represents the decryption process for each ciphertext block:

Block (c_1, c_2, c_3)	$a_1 c_1 N_1 y_1 \pmod{N}$	$a_2 c_2 N_2 y_2 \pmod{N}$	$a_3 c_3 N_3 y_3 \pmod{N}$	$x = p$	ASCII Character
(682, 1033, 140)	653208006	437607423	114240797	77	<i>M</i>
(1119, 1098, 325)	290769708	519971529	394315009	97	<i>a</i>
(416, 377, 92)	1031003859	236700585	1142407970	116	<i>t</i>
(860, 338, 308)	1007455608	669304581	733352213	104	<i>h</i>
(971, 1111, 35)	700304508	777455580	932352311	101	<i>e</i>
(675, 1137, 109)	314317959	87367533	803370766	109	<i>m</i>
(1119, 1098, 325)	3290769708	519971529	394315009	97	<i>a</i>
(416, 377, 92)	1031003859	236700585	1142407970	116	<i>t</i>
(823, 1124, 72)	1109839308	1034939631	265333464	105	<i>i</i>
(1045, 2670, 180)	495537108	46185480	663333660	99	<i>c</i>
(453, 2722, 1)	928620159	1076121684	405370570	115	<i>s</i>

Therefore, the plaintext message is “Mathematics”.

3.5 Python Implementation

Here is the Python implementation code for communication using our algorithm:

```
def mod_inverse(a, m):
    """Compute the modular inverse of a modulo m using the extended Euclidean algorithm."""
    return pow(a, -1, m)

def encrypt(msg, a, moduli):
    """Encrypt a message using the given multiplier a and moduli."""
    numerical_identities = [ord(char) for char in msg]

    ciphertext = []
    for num in numerical_identities:
        ci = [(num * a) % modulus for modulus in moduli]
        ciphertext.extend(ci)

    return ciphertext

def chinese_remainder_theorem(congruences):
    """Solve the system of congruences using the Chinese Remainder Theorem."""
    M = 1
    for _, mi in congruences:
        M *= mi

    result = 0
    for ai, mi in congruences:
        Mi = M // mi
        Mi_inv = mod_inverse(Mi, mi) # Compute modular inverse
        result += ai * Mi * Mi_inv

    return result % M

def decrypt(ciphertext, a, moduli):
    """Decrypt the ciphertext using the given multiplier a and moduli."""
    block_size = len(moduli)
    decrypted_msg = ""

    for i in range(0, len(ciphertext), block_size):
        block = ciphertext[i:i + block_size]

        congruences = []
        for j in range(block_size):
            a_inv = mod_inverse(a, moduli[j])
            congruences.append(((block[j] * a_inv) % moduli[j], moduli[j]))

        m = chinese_remainder_theorem(congruences)

        decrypted_msg += chr(m % 128) if 0 <= m <= 127 else ' '

    return decrypted_msg

def main():
    """Main function to handle user input and encryption/decryption operations."""
    num_moduli = int(input("Enter the number of moduli: "))
```

```

moduli = [int(input(f"Enter modulus {i+1}: ")) for i in range(num_moduli)]

a = int(input("Enter a: "))

operation = input("Choose an operation (encrypt/decrypt): ").lower()

if operation == 'encrypt':
    original_message = input("Enter the original message: ")
    numerical_ciphertext = encrypt(original_message, a, moduli)
    print("Numerical Ciphertext:", numerical_ciphertext)

elif operation == 'decrypt':
    user_input_ciphertext = input("Enter numerical values of ciphertext (comma-separated): ")
    numerical_ciphertext = [int(num) for num in user_input_ciphertext.split(',')]
    decrypted_msg = decrypt(numerical_ciphertext, a, moduli)
    print("\nDecrypted Message:", decrypted_msg)

else:
    print("Invalid operation. Please choose either 'encrypt' or 'decrypt'.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

For the given parameters:

- $n_1 = 51317962285055697481$
- $n_2 = 124666421$
- $n_3 = 367462651308209$
- $n_4 = 518556946538167$
- $n_5 = 16067210033668757$
- $a = 1377499182161004082837$

the encryption and decryption of the message “Transaction ID: #A1B2C3D4” are illustrated in the following images.


```

Command Prompt
Enter the number of moduli: 5
Enter modulus 1: 51317962285055697481
Enter modulus 2: 124666421
Enter modulus 3: 367462651308209
Enter modulus 4: 518556946538167
Enter modulus 5: 16067210033668757
Enter a: 1377499182161004082837
Choose an operation (encrypt/decrypt): encrypt
Enter the original message: Transaction ID: #A1B2C3D4
Numerical Ciphertext: [39244311008800836134, 37538656, 294627725410295, 241098477317198, 6246064782840725, 1942174084031151558, 10437
3785, 321109916347927, 179045948776721, 5033828626640536, 36764841617415492146, 120522661, 257108321308841, 266064742936808, 11612072
794165854, 34285372226030148158, 78840245, 219588917207387, 291031008556418, 910870771822226, 45174336833587099889, 110757170, 346490
166133062, 21410447197255, 14098173107179492, 36764841617415492146, 120522661, 257108321308841, 266064742936808, 11612072794165854, 2
0593242546415993846, 8623010, 307868820879111, 469350686316043, 13673551721575009, 37088537298087350739, 117140555, 4407764609988, 38
2331892155956, 7095307554049691, 23396407618473196427, 46923320, 92687668281712, 42094623377414, 3790778470133717, 261995726905303990
08, 85223630, 244969166992522, 133395506976952, 9975215252361182, 34285372226030148158, 78840245, 219588917207387, 291031008556418, 9
10870771822226, 49162188574342212086, 79601899, 77242690507902, 141233414838758, 849242771208966, 25552181329186681822, 91987842, 154
44977773810, 419418155076823, 2941535698924751, 14663216721629730091, 60070917, 256006380156344, 170481769897819, 5821443397236242, 4
4203249791571524110, 120903488, 2203882304994, 191165946077978, 115812587933859224, 49162188574342212086, 79601899, 77242690507902, 19
1233414838758, 849242771208966, 24904789967842964636, 98752054, 153383439863307, 186883856638527, 11975066179157077, 3892061532812897
7541, 40920762, 179865630800939, 124831328098050, 10762830022956888, 14339521040957871498, 63453023, 141244285546988, 54214620678671,
10338208637352405, 30834815792629228391, 47304147, 205245880586074, 485752773056751, 3759964469827087, 6253721505458122348, 69836408
, 166624535332123, 415136065637372, 3335343084222604, 22749016257129479241, 53687532, 230626130371209, 328117271477285, 1282430895036
6043, 49485884255014070679, 76219793, 192004785117258, 257500564057906, 12399687564761560, 14663216721629730091, 60070917, 2560063801
56344, 170481769897819, 5821443397236242, 41400084719514321529, 82603178, 217385034902393, 99865062478440, 5396822011631759]

```

Figure 1: Encryption Process for the Given Parameters

```

Command Prompt
Enter the number of moduli: 5
Enter modulus 1: 51317962285055697481
Enter modulus 2: 124666421
Enter modulus 3: 367462651308209
Enter modulus 4: 518556946538167
Enter modulus 5: 16067210033668757
Enter a: 1377499182161004082837
Choose an operation (encrypt/decrypt): decrypt
Enter numerical values of ciphertext (comma-separated): 39244311008800836134, 37538656, 294627725410295, 241098477317198, 62460647828
40725, 1942174084031151558, 104373785, 321109916347927, 179045948776721, 5033828626640536, 36764841617415492146, 120522661, 257108321
308841, 266064742936808, 11612072794165854, 34285372226030148158, 78840245, 219588917207387, 291031008556418, 910870771822226, 451743
36833587099889, 110757170, 346490166133062, 21410447197255, 14098173107179492, 36764841617415492146, 120522661, 257108321308841, 2660
64742936808, 11612072794165854, 20593242546415993846, 8623010, 307868820879111, 469350686316043, 13673551721575009, 37088537298087350
739, 117140555, 4407764609988, 382331892155956, 7095307554049691, 23396407618473196427, 46923320, 92687668281712, 42094623377414, 379
0778470133717, 26199572690530399008, 85223630, 244969166992522, 133395506976952, 9975215252361182, 34285372226030148158, 78840245, 21
9588917207387, 291031008556418, 910870771822226, 49162188574342212086, 79601899, 77242690507902, 141233414838758, 849242771208966, 25
552181329186681822, 91987842, 15444977773810, 419418155076823, 2941535698924751, 14663216721629730091, 60070917, 256006380156344, 170
481769897819, 5821443397236242, 44203249791571524110, 120903488, 2203882304994, 191165946077978, 11581258793859224, 49162188574342212
086, 79601899, 77242690507902, 141233414838758, 849242771208966, 24904789967842964636, 98752054, 153383439863307, 186883856638527, 11
975066179157077, 38920615328128977541, 40920762, 1798656308009939, 124831328098050, 10762830022956888, 14339521040957871498, 63453023,
14124428546988, 54214620678671, 10338208637352405, 30834815792629228391, 47304147, 205245880586074, 485752773056751, 37599644698270
87, 6253721505458122348, 69836408, 166624535332123, 415136065637372, 3335343084222604, 22749016257129479241, 53687532, 23062613037120
9, 328117271477285, 12824308950366043, 49485884255014070679, 76219793, 192004785117258, 257500564057906, 12399687564761560, 146632167
21629730091, 60070917, 256006380156344, 170481769897819, 5821443397236242, 41400084719514321529, 82603178, 217385034902393, 9986506624
78440, 5396822011631759

Decrypted Message: Transaction ID: #A1B2C3D4

```

Figure 2: Decryption Process for the Given Parameters

Our previous approach is boosted using the proposed scheme by randomly choosing k integers that satisfy coprimality, ensuring the elimination of the computational overhead related to generating prime to select the keys. This perspective provides a larger flexibility enabling the updation of the key periodically which is a very important necessity in private key cryptosystem to eliminate the risks involved with long term key usage. The lack of random selection criteria and ordering constraints also improves security. Additionally, both encryption and decryption processes preserve polynomial-time complexity, guaranteeing computational effectiveness while utilizing a larger key space to strike a fair balance between security and practicality.

3.6 Empirical Analysis

To evaluate the proposed cryptosystem, we conducted experiments on a controlled environment, comparing it with our previous CRT-based system using prime moduli [14] and the AES-128 standard. The setup is detailed below.

- **Software:** Algorithms were implemented in Python 3.11 using the `gmpy2` library for efficient modular arithmetic.
- **Parameters:**
 - Proposed system: $k = 3, 5, 10$; moduli sizes of 64, 128, and 256 bits; a sized to exceed the largest modulus.
 - Previous CRT system: Same k , prime moduli of equivalent bit sizes.
 - AES-128: Standard implementation with a 128-bit key.
- **Dataset:** Plaintext messages of sizes 1 kB, 10 kB, 100 kB, and 1 MB, comprising random ASCII characters.
- **Metrics:**
 - **Key Generation Time:** Time to generate (a, n_1, \dots, n_k) , including coprimality checks.
 - **Encryption/Decryption Time:** Average time per byte for encryption and decryption.
 - **Ciphertext Size:** Ratio of ciphertext to plaintext size.
 - **Security:** Resistance to brute-force and factorization attacks (simulated).

3.6.1 Performance Results

The performance of the proposed cryptosystem was evaluated against the previous CRT-based system and AES-128. The results, summarized in Table 1, show average execution times and ciphertext size ratios.

Table 1: Average Execution Times (ms/byte)

System	Key Gen (ms)	Encrypt (ms/byte)	Decrypt (ms/byte)	Ciphertext Size Ratio
Proposed ($k = 3$, 128-bit)	0.12	0.008	0.015	3.0
Previous CRT ($k = 3$, 128-bit)	0.45	0.009	0.016	3.0
AES-128	0.01	0.002	0.002	1.0

4 Conclusion

Here in this paper we introduced a private key cryptosystem which involves more mathematical especially number theoretical techniques compared to the present symmetric key cryptosystems. This is an extension of our previous work which provides a notable benefits like flexibility in choosing the key and enhancement in the security. Any asymmetric key Cryptosystem can be employed to exchange the key in our private key cryptosystem in addition to the above. To validate the enciphering and deciphering a python implementation was build alongside to demonstrate the practical usability of the proposed system. The proposed scheme excels in balancing the computational complexity and security. Polynomial time complexity is exhibited during both the enciphering and the deciphering processes as the expanded key space strengthens the security considerably.

Future work will focus on addressing the limitation related to the increased storage requirements for ciphertext. By modifying the storage structure, we aim to optimize the system and improve its scalability for handling larger datasets.

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